

THE PROBLEM OF IDEAS ABOUT DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL HELP IN LOCAL AND FOREIGN RESEARCH

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the analysis of methodological bases of providing psychological support in local and foreign scientific research activities. The author's model of multimodal integrative systemic therapy, which is effective when used in psychological services of higher educational institutions, is described. There are also comments on the problem of ideas about psychological help.

Key words: Scientific research, methodology, psychological support, idea, multimodal, MIST, P. Grayson.

Psychological assistance to student youth is a relatively new humanitarian discipline, the emergence of which is associated with a number of factors of modern life: the globalization of higher education, the increase in neuropsychic stress in students, both of which are rapidly changing educational programs. The need for adaptation and a flexible labor market, etc. The school of psychological services and centers inevitably raised the issue of developing the conceptual framework of psychological support as a type of psychologist's activity in a specific educational environment.

The complexity of developing a model of psychological support for students is related to the heterogeneity and multi-directionality of various schools of counseling and psychotherapy based on it, which leads to problems when trying to create a methodology for practice. Even in countries where psychological services have existed for a long time, there is no agreed model for providing psychological support to student youth and does not exist, because all professionals base their work on different theoretical foundations.

An analysis of publications on university therapy shows the regular use of various modifications of the psychoanalytic method, decision-oriented cognitive-behavioral therapy, paradoxical interventions, and systematic family therapy. In general, as P. Grayson pointed out, university psychologists deal with special problems such as alcohol or drug abuse, eating disorders, and special student groups such as first-year students, rather than analyzing their effectiveness applied theories. There is also a tendency to use short-term therapy.¹

In our country, as in other post-Soviet republics, there are difficulties in choosing the methodological basis of providing psychological support to students. A 2009 study of 69 educational psychologists showed that 49.2% of them did not have any special training in this

¹ Grayson, P.A. Psychodynamic psychotherapy with students and graduate students /P.A. Grayson // Journal of Practical Psychology and Psychoanalysis. Quarterly scientific and practical journal of electronic publications. – 2009;

or that psychotherapeutic field, based only on knowledge gained during university studies (or retraining). tmagan.. The remaining 50.8 percent of the psychologists surveyed received additional training of varying quality: from a 7-year course in Gestalt therapy to a 2-day workshop in art therapy. Thus, 20.7% of the research participants used gestalt therapy, 11.6% art therapy, 10.1% family therapy, 8.7% neurolinguistic programming, 5.8% each of catatim-imaginative therapy, body-oriented therapy and existential therapy, 4.3 percent trained. Each % - behavior therapy and fairy tale therapy, 2.9% - psychosynthesis. One person from each (1.4% of the respondents) participated in seminars on systematic family groups, coaching, dance-movement therapy, humanistic psychotherapy, group analysis, Jung sand therapy² according to B. Hellinger's method. Undoubtedly, many university psychologists have minimal knowledge, providing psychological help requires certain skills in diagnosing the problem, setting goals and objectives, finding resources, assessing the level of suicide risk, etc.

The existing variety of fields of counseling and psychotherapy does not answer the question of which of them is more suitable for solving students' problems. However, our research showed that half of the psychologists working at the university do not have modern theories of psychological care and, accordingly, do not have the necessary skills and abilities. In addition, many short-term specialized courses are of little use for complex activities such as providing psychological care. Thus, we can note the low professional level of local psychologists working in the higher education system in the field of consultation, as well as the urgency of searching for methodological foundations for creating a model of psychological support for students.

Today, it is possible to note the existing tendency to reject methodological monism. A modern psychologist can prepare to provide psychological support in several directions at the same time. This model is called "Learning from many masters" [6]. Therefore, many psychologists rely not on a single psychotherapeutic project in the training and further development of their methods, but on various possibilities that lead to the creation of a generalized theory. At the same time, focusing on different models, including philosophical models, first of all meets the requirements of modern practice, which takes into account the diversity of clients and the scope of their problems.

One of the models that the student has shown to be effective in working with young people is the multimodal integrative systems therapy (MIST) that we are developing. It can be used to provide psychological support to individuals, couples, families and systems in difficult life situations. Let's explain each of the elements included in the name.

Modality (Latin *modus* - size, method, image) in the broadest sense is a category that describes the manner of action or attitude to action. By multimodality, we understood the possibility of using different factors (cognitive, emotional, behavioral, social, cultural, family) in analyzing the problem and searching for its solution. In addition, the term "modality" is also used to refer to individual methods of psychotherapy and psychological counseling, so "multimodal" means the possibility of a psychologist to focus on different therapeutic schools and different factors when working with a client.

Through integration, we understood the possibility of combining and applying different theories and directions of therapy, according to various sources, their number today is from

² Olifirovich, N.I. Psychological service of the university: features of advisory activity / N. Olifirovich // Bulletin of Brestskaga University. – Series 3. Philology, Pedagogy, Psychology. - No. 2, 2010. - P.132-141.

400 to 1000.³ However, not all of them are original, unique and revolutionary - unlike the natural sciences, the "revolution" in psychotherapy does not lead to a radical change of the scientific paradigm. When creating new directions, only the redistribution of spheres of influence is carried out, and the new paradigms themselves do not prevail.

When we talk about changes in the psychotherapeutic space, we must understand that we are only talking about changes in intellectual fashion. Each new school "absorbs and digests" problems, diseases, emerging contradictions and produces new and new practices. This process, according to scientists, is endless. It should be noted that a modern student-psychologist in the process of learning can not only master various psychotherapeutic models and their practical application, but also cannot study in depth. Thus, the future psychologist chooses the direction of his activity almost blindly, randomly "adjacent" to one direction or another. Therefore, the possibility of combining individual theoretical positions, ideas, and methods related to different therapeutic schools is effective and is often used by theorists and practicing psychologists.

The term "system" in the name of this model is also associated with certain theoretical constructs used to describe various phenomena of human life. It is known that the development of psychological practice has been in the direction of finding a single cause of mental disorders and dysfunctions for a long time. The results of the studies of that time are presented in the form of a chain of linear relationships that reflect certain stereotypes of our thinking. However, since the 1940s, various studies have been conducted not only about the suffering person, but also about his social system, primarily the family.

Note that today there is no single systemic therapy. This concept covers many different heterogeneous models, which allows us to consider it as a broad meta-definition. Many researchers are attracted to systems theory as a universal theory because it *"offers a single interdisciplinary metatheoretical language for phenomena at any level - from the cellular organism to the entire society"*.⁴

In a broad sense, a system is "a set of elements or objects related to the objects themselves and their properties." For its definition and description, the system must be separated from the outside world, which means that there is an observer who decides what counts as the "system" and what counts as the "environment".

In our model, the use of the concept of "system" involves its representation through a number of individual parameters. There is no doubt that all parameters of the system are interrelated and affect each other. A change in one of them leads to certain changes in others. However, despite the interdependence of any system parameters, we propose to divide them into three separate clusters: structural, procedural and historical parameters. Each of the clusters makes it possible to describe important aspects of the system's activity through a number of indicators, which are its units of analysis. Note that, in contrast to concrete sciences, where the unit of analysis can be clearly defined by specially measured variables, in psychology (as in other social and philosophical sciences) this unit is more declarative and sub is a positive value. Nevertheless, the distribution of such units of analysis allows solving the problem of system description. Structural parameters are the most detailed in the literature on family

³ Sosland, A. The fundamental structure of the psychotherapeutic method, or how to create your own school in psychotherapy / A. Sosland. – M.: Logos, 1999. – 368 p.

⁴ Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

psychology and psychotherapy. Most researchers agree to distinguish them from a set of indicators that describe the functioning of the family system. These include cohesion, hierarchy, flexibility, external and internal boundaries, and role structure.

As for procedural and historical parameters, we considered that they can be separated according to the principle of "verticality - horizontality". Thus, procedural parameters combine indicators determined in the horizontal section of the system (time dynamics of the studied system) and historical parameters in the vertical (the history of this system, relative to another). larger systems in which it is included). Providing psychological help to a student involves analyzing his personal characteristics, desires, motives, goals, etc. through the prism of a problematic situation. It should also be taken into account that every student is a member of his family system, and also enters into the system of social relations with the university, dormitory, friends, acquaintances and social environment, that is, a social network.

Therefore, for the breadth of system analysis, it is recommended to take into account the characteristics of different levels of its operation:

- *individual level describes the functioning of a person (family member) as a system element;*
- *the microsystem level refers to the functioning of the nuclear (nuclear) family, which includes parents and their children;*
- *macrosystem level describes the activity of a large family consisting of three or more generations;*
- *the level of the megasystem corresponds to the activity of the family bordering on the social environment.*

In the work of the university's psychological service, a psychologist usually deals with an individual client - a student who has applied for psychological help.

However, often the client's actual problems are related not only to his personality, history, or life dynamics, but also to his relationship with his parents or extended family and social environment. Therefore, analyzing and taking into account all the parameters that allow to provide many perspectives when working on psychological support.

Thus, for example, in order to work most effectively with the symptomatic behavior of the student as a member of the family and as a separate social unit, it is important to see the projection of this symptom at different levels of the activity of the family and social environment. , that is, analysis as a systemic phenomenon. For example, the presentation of a problem such as low academic performance can be related to the microstem level of performance, where the analysis of historical parameters, in particular, reveals that the student's parents did not have a higher education. loyalty to the family system, he performs a series of self-destructive behaviors, such as skipping classes, not preparing for them, losing interest in studies, etc. In the situation where the highlighted problem is defined by the student as intrapersonal (experiences, circumstances, individual characteristics, etc.), it is analyzed using various methods and based on systematic assumptions. Resources in this model are other levels of system activity that allow us to rely on "healthy" properties and relationships.

Predictions of the problem at different levels of system activity are based on a holistic principle that reflects the characteristics of the entire system. This methodological principle

allows the psychologist to move freely in the problem area of the individual client and choose the most suitable psychotherapeutic intervention strategy for the case.

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